

Title: Discovery of Logic in Language that scientists have not described yet

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INTRODUCTION:

Scientists fail to define intelligence as a set of natural laws (like I did). Therefore, AI is not an artificial implementation of natural intelligence.

As a consequence, the field of AI and NLP isn't scientific. A science delivers generic solutions, while AI is limited to engineering: specific solutions to specific problems. And engineered solutions are limited to perform routine tasks.

AIM:

To solve fundamental problems in the field of AI and NLP, by uplifting this field towards a science.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

I am using fundamental science (logic and laws of nature) instead of cognitive science (simulation of behavior), because:

- Autonomous reasoning requires both intelligence and language;
- Intelligence and language are natural phenomena;
- Natural phenomena obey laws of nature;
- Laws of nature (and logic) are investigated using fundamental science.

RESULTS:

By defining intelligence as a set of natural laws, I have discovered logical structures in natural language that scientists have not described yet. It extends Aristotelian Logic. Proof of the pudding: <http://mafait.org/challenge/>. These logical structures has enabled me to close the loop for natural intelligence and natural language, which uplifts this field towards a science.

Just to illustrate the characteristics of a science: The field of electromagnetism is scientifically understood, because scientists are able to close the loop for electricity, magnetism, movement and light. Scientists are able:

- to convert electricity to light, and to convert light back to electricity;
- to convert electricity to magnetism, and magnetism back to electricity;
- to convert magnetism to movement, and movement back to magnetism.

In a similar way, I have closed the loop for natural intelligence and natural language, which uplifts this field towards a science. As a result, my software is able:

- to convert readable sentences – with a limited grammar – to a logic that is not described by scientists yet;
- to derive new knowledge from this extended logic;

- and to express the derived knowledge as readable and autonomously word-by-word constructed sentences.

The logical rules of my reasoner are (almost) language-independent. So, I can add any language, just by configuring my reasoner for this new language, and a little programming. As such, my reasoner is already able to read and write in English, Spanish, French and Dutch. And currently, I am adding the Chinese language.

I defy anyone to beat the simplest results of my Controlled Natural Language (CNL) reasoner in a generic way: from natural language, through algorithms, back to natural language. See: <http://mafait.org/challenge/>

It is open source software: <http://mafait.org/download/>

PS: I am used to comments like: “It has been done 40 years ago”. But no one seems able to show it to me in a demonstration. The truth is: bits and pieces are already been described. But no one else is able to integrate those bits and pieces in one working system.

CONCLUSIONS:

The field of AI and NLP has fundamental problems. We really need to uplift this field of engineering towards a science.

KEYWORDS:

AI; NLP; natural intelligence; natural language; fundamental; Aristotle; logic.

BIOGRAPHY:

Menno started as an undergraduate Software Tester. Now he is testing – and improving – the fundamentals of the field of AI and NLP.